

PHOTO-IODINATION OF CITRIC ACID IN AQUEOUS SOLUTION

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Citric acid has been iodinated with aqueous iodine in presence of light at different temperatures and different concentrations of the acceptor and active molecules.

The reaction shows an induction period and there is a progressive diminution of the velocity constant with decrease in concentration of the acceptor molecules; but there is also an increase of the unimolecular constant with decrease in concentration of the active molecules.

In the previous paper (Mukherjee and Goswami, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, 21, 237) KI was avoided and the reaction was carried out with sodium tartrate with aqueous iodine and certain peculiarities were observed. Expecting that the same peculiarities would be observed in other photo-iodination process, the present piece of investigation was undertaken.

EXPERIMENTAL

Resublimed iodine was mixed with $\frac{1}{4}$ its weight of KI and sublimed again to remove traces of chlorine etc. This iodine was dissolved in conductivity water by shaking in a shaker. Pure Merck 'Extrapure' citric acid was dissolved in conductivity water. Equal volumes of solutions of iodine and citric acid, whose concentrations (before mixing) are given in each table, were mixed in the reaction vessel in a thermostat in the dark. Immediately 3 c. c. of the reaction mixture were withdrawn and titrated against approximately 0.001N- $\text{Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ by using a microburette. The source of light was a Point-o-lite lamp of 150 C. P. By keeping the centre of the lamp at a distance of 42.5 cm. from the reaction cell, the intensity of light was kept the same throughout the experiment. The mixture in the reaction cell was then exposed to light, made parallel by means of lens. Heat rays were cut off by allowing the light to pass through a filter of $\text{N}/20\text{-CuSO}_4$. At various intervals of time, measured by means of a stop watch, 3 c. c. of the reaction mixture were withdrawn and titrated as in the dark reaction.

Since after each withdrawal of 3 c. c. of the reaction mixture, a vacuum space occurred in which I_2 could vaporise, and since it might diffuse through the reaction cell, it was first investigated whether there was any error due to these two factors; the escape of iodine due to these factors was found to be quite negligible.

Table XI gives the reaction rate in dark at 20°; the dark reaction is unimolecular. k is the unimolecular constant calculated according to the equation $k = 1/t \log 10 \frac{a}{a-x}$, where a represents the initial concentration of I_2 and $(a-x)$, the concentration I_2 after t minutes.

The reactions shown in Tables I to XI were carried at 20°, while those shown in Tables XIV and XV were carried at 30°. The temperature coefficients at two different concentrations of citric acid are shown in Table XVI.

TABLE I

Citric acid = 1 M. $I_2 = 0.1614 N/50$.
Written filter blue used.

Time.	Thio.	k .
0 min.	2.87 c.c.	
15	2.62	
30	2.44	.00228
90	1.80	.00222
120	1.50	.00223
	Mean.	.00224

TABLE II

Citric acid = 0.5 M. Conc. of I_2 and filter same as in Table I.

Time	Thio.	k .
0 min.	3.00 c.c. Induction	
10	3.00	period
30	2.78	.00165
60	2.58	.00165
90	2.36	.00137
120	2.20	.00130
	Mean.	.00149

TABLE III

Citric acid = 0.25 M. I_2 and filter same as in Table I.

Time.	Thio.	k .
0 min.	2.68 c.c. Induction	
15	2.68	period.
30	2.58	.00110
60	2.40	.00109
90	2.22	.00109
	Mean	.00109

TABLE IV

Citric acid = 0.125 M. I_2 and filter same as in Table I.

Time.	Thio.	k .
0 min.	3.82 c.c. Induction	
15	3.82	period.
30	3.70	.000928
60	3.48	.000900
120	2.96	.00105
	Mean	.000869

TABLE V

Citric acid = 0.1 M. I_2 and filter same as in Table I.

Time.	Thio.	k .
0 min.	5.00 c.c. Induction	
15	5.00	period
30	4.84	.000916
60	4.54	.000931
90	4.25	.000920
120	4.00	.000921
	Mean.	.000929

TABLE VI

Citric acid = 0.1 M. Conc. of $I_2 = 0.1614 N/50$. Blue filter.

Time.	Thio.	k .
0 min.	3.43 c.c.	
15	3.33	
30	3.22	.000967
45	3.12	.000910
60	3.01	.001173
90	2.82	.000942
	Mean	.000960

Tables II—V show an induction period.

TABLE VII

$I_2=0.1614N/100$.
Citric acid and filter same as in Table VI.

Time.	Thio.	k
0 min.	2.28 c.c.	
15	2.20	
30	2.11	0.00112
60	1.98	.00101
90	1.86	.00121
	Mean	0.00114

TABLE VIII

$I_2=0.1614 N/160$.
Citric acid and filter same as in Table VI.

Time.	Thio.	k
0 min.	4.25 c.c. Induction period.	
15	4.25	
30	4.00	0.00168
60	3.65	.000147
90	3.28	.00150
105	3.04	.00161
	Mean	.00158

TABLE IX

$I_2=0.1614 N/200$.
Citric acid & filter same as in Table VI.

Time.	Thio.	k
0 min.	1.64 c.c. Induction period.	
10	1.64	
30	1.43	0.00161
45	1.35	.00169
60	1.28	.00160
90	1.06	.00161
	Mean	.00161

TABLE X

$I_2=0.1614 N/200$. Citric acid & filter same as in Table VI.

Time.	Thio.	k
0 min.	2.22 c.c. Induction period.	
15	2.22	
30	2.22	
45	2.09	0.00175
60	1.96	.00180
75	1.85	.00178
	Mean	0.00177

TABLE XI

Citric acid & I_2 same as in Table V. Dark reaction.

Time	Thio	k
0 min.	3.22 c.c.	
60	3.17	0.000113
145	3.10	.000114
235	3.02	.00094

TABLE XII

Variation of k with the decrease of conc. of active molecules (I_2).

Conc.	k	Ref. table.
0.1614 N/50	0.000929	V
.1614 N/80	.000960	VI
.1614 N/100	.00114	VII
.1614 N/160	.00156	VIII
.1614 N/200	.00161	IX
.1614 N/260	.00177	X

Induction period is observed in Tables VIII to X.

TABLE XIII

Variation of the value k as the conc. of the acceptor molecules decreases.

Conc.	k	Reference Table.
0.1 M	0.00224	I
0.50	.00149	II
0.025	.00109	III
0.125	0.000958	IV
0.1	.000929	V

TABLE XIV

0.25 M-Citric acid 0.1614 N/50-Iodine and blue filter, Temp.=30.

Time	Thio.	k
0 min	1.90 c.c. Induction period	
15	1.90	
30	1.76	0.00222
60	1.52	.00215
90	1.32	.00211
120	1.14	.00211
	Mean	.00215

TABLE XV

0.1 M-Citric acid, $I_2=0.1614 N/50$ blue filter, Temp.=30°.

Time.	Thio.	k
0 min	2.46 c.c.	
20	2.22	
40	2.02	0.00205;
60	1.83	.00204
90	1.60	.00203
	Mean	.00204

Mean .00215

TABLE XVI

Concentration of citric acid.	Iodine content.	k at 20°.	k_{t+10} at 30°	Temp. coeff.
				$\frac{k(t+10)}{k}$
0.25 <i>M</i>	0.1611 <i>N</i> /50	0.00109	0.00215	1.9
0.1 <i>M</i>	0.1614 <i>N</i> /50	.00093	.00204	2.2

The decrease of the unimolecular constant with increase in the concentration of the active molecules might be, we believe, ascribed to a greater chance of the active molecules being deactivated by collision with other unactivated molecules of the same species present inside the solution on account of the greater proximity of these (unactivated) molecules to the active molecules present at higher than at lower concentration.

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